

LINEAR GEOMETRY: VECTOR ALGEBRA IN AFFINE SPACES

TARAS BANAKH, IVAN HETMAN, VLAD PSHYK

ABSTRACT. Linear Geometry describes geometric properties that depend on the notion of a line. The fundamental structure studied in Linear Geometry is the structure of a liner. It is a set of points endowed with a family of subsets called lines. This family should satisfy two axioms, one of which is the first Euclid axiom postulating that any distinct points belong to a unique line. A liner is an affine space if it is regular, satisfies the Parallelity Postulate, and contains three non-collinear points. In this survey paper we discuss vectors and scalars in affine spaces and show that any Thalesian affine space has the canonical structure of an affine space over the corps of scalars. Using this structure, we study the automorphism group of a Desarguesian affine space.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is the fifth survey in the series of surveys that describe the contents of the monograph “Linear Geometry and Algebra” [2]. The first survey [3] concentrated at properties of liners that depend on flat hulls (flats, ranks, regularity, parallelity); the second survey [4] discussed completions and projectivizations of lines; the third survey [5] discussed Desarguesian, Pappian and Thalesian liners; the fourth survey [6] discusses some special automorphisms of liners (dilations, translations, and hypershears) and some special bijections between lines in affine and projective liners (line projections, line translations, line affinities, line perspectivities, line projectivities). In this survey we define vectors and scalars in affine spaces and show that scalars in an affine space form a corps. Also we show that Thalesian affine spaces carry the structure of an affine space over its corps of scalars, and apply this structure to studying the automorphism group of a Desarguesian affine space. The material of this survey covers Chapters 14, 16, 17, 18, 19 of the book [2].

1. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we recall some basic notions of Linear Geometry, needed for understanding the main results of this survey.

A *liner* is a set X of *points*, endowed with a family \mathcal{L} of subsets of X called *lines* such that the following two axioms are satisfied:

- any two distinct points belong to a unique line;
- any line contains at least two distinct points.

For two distinct points x, y of a liner X , we denote by \overline{xy} the unique line containing those points. If $x = y$, then we put $\overline{xy} := \{x\} = \{y\}$.

A liner X is *κ -long* for a cardinal κ if every line L in X has cardinality $|L| \geq \kappa$.

Each subset $A \subseteq X$ of a liner (X, \mathcal{L}) carries the line structure

$$\mathcal{L}_A := \{L \cap A : L \in \mathcal{L} \wedge |L \cap A| \geq 2\}$$

turning A into a liner, called a *subliner* of the liner (X, \mathcal{L}) .

A subset $A \subseteq X$ of a liner X is called *flat* if $\overline{xy} \subseteq A$ for any points $x, y \in A$. For a subset $A \subseteq X$ its *flat hull* \overline{A} is the smallest flat set in X that contains the set A . The *rank* $\|A\|$ of a set $A \subseteq X$ is the smallest cardinality of a subset $B \subseteq X$ such that $A \subseteq \overline{B}$. Flat subsets of rank 3 in a liner are called *planes*. The *dimension* $\dim(X)$ of a liner X is the unique cardinal κ such that $1 + \kappa = \|X\|$.

A subset A of a liner X is called

- *independent* if $x \notin \overline{A \setminus \{x\}}$ for all $x \in A$;
- *maximal independent* if $A = M$ for any independent set $M \subseteq X$ that contains A .

For two flats A, B in a liner X , we say that A is *subparallel* to B and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \subseteq \overline{B \cup \{a\}}$ for all $a \in A$. We say that flats $A, B \subseteq X$ are *parallel* and write $A \parallel B$ if $A \parallel B$ and $B \parallel A$.

A liner X is called

- *Playfair* if for every plane $P \subseteq X$, line $L \subseteq P$ and point $x \in P \setminus L$, there exists a unique line $\Lambda \subseteq P$ such that $x \in \Lambda$ and $\Lambda \cap L = \emptyset$;
- *affine* if for every points $o, x, y \in X$ and $p \in \overline{xy} \setminus \overline{ox}$ there exists a unique point $u \in \overline{oy}$ such that $\overline{up} \cap \overline{ox} = \emptyset$;
- *regular* if for every flat $A \subseteq X$ and points $o \in A, b \in X \setminus A$ we have $\overline{A \cup \{b\}} = \bigcup_{a \in A} \bigcup_{y \in \overline{ob}} \overline{ay}$;
- an *affine space* if X is 3-long, affine, regular, and has rank $\|X\| \geq 3$.

By [2, 4.1.1], every 4-long affine liner is Playfair and regular. Consequently, every 4-long affine liner of rank ≥ 3 is an affine space. By [2, 3.3.17] any two lines in an affine liner X have the same cardinality, denoted by $|X|_2$ and called the *order* of the affine liner X .

A bijective map $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between two liners (X, \mathcal{L}_X) and (Y, \mathcal{L}_Y) is called a *liner isomorphism* if $\mathcal{L}_Y = \{F[L] : L \in \mathcal{L}_X\}$. An *automorphism* of a liner X is any liner isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow X$. The set $\text{Aut}(X)$ of automorphisms of a liner X endowed with the operation of composition is a group, called the *automorphism group* of the liner X .

An automorphism $F : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called a *dilation* of X if for every line L in X , the line $F[L]$ is parallel to L . The set of all dilations of a liner X forms a normal subgroup $\text{Dil}(X)$ in the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of the liner X .

A dilation $F : X \rightarrow X$ of a liner X is called a

- *translation* if either $F(x) = x$ of all $x \in X$ or $F(x) \neq x$ for all $x \in X$;
- *homothety* if $F(o) = o$ for some point $o \in X$.

By [2, 12.2.6], the set $\text{Tra}(X)$ of all translations of an affine space X is a normal subgroup of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$.

A liner X is called

- *Desarguesian* if for any distinct lines A, B, C in X and distinct points $o \in A \cap B \cap C$, $a, a' \in A, b, b' \in B, c, c' \in C$, the set $T := (\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'}) \cup (\overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}) \cup (\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'})$ has rank $\|T\| \in \{0, 2\}$;
- *Thalesian* if for any distinct parallel lines A, B, C in X and points $a, a' \in A, b, b' \in B, c, c' \in C$ with $\overline{ab} \cap \overline{a'b'} = \emptyset = \overline{bc} \cap \overline{b'c'}$, we have $\overline{ac} \cap \overline{a'c'} = \emptyset$;
- *translation* if for any points $x, y \in X$ there exists a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $T(x) = y$;
- *∂ -translation* if for any line $L \subseteq X$ there are distinct points $x, y \in L$ and a translation $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that $T(x) = y$;
- *dilation* if for any points $o, x \in X$ and $y \in \overline{ox}$ there exists a dilation $D : X \rightarrow X$ such that $D(o) = o$ and $D(x) = y$.

Every translation liner is ∂ -translation. By [2, 14.4.8+16.8.5], an affine space X is

- Thalesian if and only if it is translation;
- Desarguesian if and only if it is dilation.

A bijection $F : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ between two lines in an affine space X is called *line projection* if there exists a line Λ such that $\overline{xy} \parallel \Lambda$ for any pair $(x, y) \in F$.

Let L, Λ be two lines in an affine space. A line projection $F : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ is called a

- a *line shift* if $L \parallel \Lambda$;
- a *line shear* if $L \cap \Lambda \neq \emptyset$;
- a *line translation* if F can be written as the composition of finitely many line shifts;
- a *line affinity* if F can be written as the composition of finitely many line shears.

Theorem 1.1 ([2, 13.4.5]). *An affine space X is Thalesian if and only if for any parallel lines L, Λ in X and points $x \in L$ and $y \in \Lambda$ there exists a unique line translation $T : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ such that $T(x) = y$.*

2. TRANSLATION EQUIVALENCE OF PAIRS IN AFFINE SPACES

Let X be an affine space. Every pair $x_0x_1 \in X^2$ is (by definition) the function $\{(0, x_0), (1, x_1)\} : 2 \rightarrow X$ on the number $2 := \{0, 1\}$. So, for any function F , we can consider the composition

$$Fx_0x_1 := \{(i, F(x_i)) : i \in 2, x_i \in \text{dom}[F]\}$$

of the functions x_0x_1 and F . The function Fx_0x_1 has domain $\text{dom}[Fx_0x_1] = \{i \in 2 : x_i \in \text{dom}[F]\}$. This domain equals 2 if and only if $\{x_0, x_1\} \subseteq \text{dom}[F]$.

Definition 2.1. Let X be an affine space. Given two pairs $ab, xy \in X^2$, we write $ab \# xy$ and say that ab and xy are *translation equivalent* if there exists a line translation T in X such that $Tab = xy$.

Proposition 2.2 ([2, 14.1.2]). *For any points $a, b, u, v, x, y \in X$ of an affine space X , the translation equivalence has the following properties:*

- (1) $ab \# ab$;
- (2) $ab \# uv \Rightarrow uv \# ab$;
- (3) $(ab \# uv \wedge uv \# xy) \Rightarrow ab \# xy$;
- (4) $ab \# uv \Rightarrow ba \# vu$;
- (5) $aa \# xx$;
- (6) If $ab \# uv$ and $a = b$, then $u = v$.

The following theorem characterizes the translation equivalence without explicit mentioning line translations.

Theorem 2.3 ([2, 14.1.4]). *Two pairs ab, uv in a (Thalesian) affine space X are translation equivalent if and only if there exist a number $n \in \omega$ (with $n \leq 2$) and pairs $x_0y_0, x_1y_1, \dots, x_ny_n \in X^2$ such that $x_0y_0 = ab$, $x_ny_n = uv$, and for every positive $i \leq n$,*

$$\overline{x_{i-1}x_i} \parallel \overline{y_{i-1}y_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{x_{i-1}y_{i-1}} \cap \overline{x_iy_i} = \emptyset.$$

Corollary 2.4 ([2, 14.2.1]). *For every pair of points $xy \in X^2$ in a (Thalesian) affine space X and every point $a \in X$, there exists a (unique) point $b \in X$ such that $ab \# xy$.*

This corollary motivates the following definition.

Definition 2.5. A pair of points $xy \in X^2$ in an affine space X is called *Thalesian* if for every point $a \in X$ there exists a *unique* point $b \in X$ such that $ab \# xy$.

Example 2.6. For every point $x \in X$ the pair xx is Thalesian.

Theorem 1.1 implies the following characterization of Thalesian affine spaces in terms of Thalesian pairs.

Corollary 2.7 ([2, 14.2.4]). *An affine space X is Thalesian if and only if every pair $xy \in X^2$ is Thalesian.*

Proposition 2.8 ([2, 14.2.6]). *If a pair $xy \in X^2$ in an affine space X is Thalesian, then the pair yx is Thalesian, too.*

Theorem 2.9 ([2, 14.2.7]). *A pair $aa' \in X^2$ in an affine space X is Thalesian if and only if*
 $\forall b, b', c, c' \in X \ ((\overline{ab} \parallel \overline{a'b'}) \wedge (\overline{bc} \parallel \overline{b'c'}) \wedge (\overline{aa'} \cap \overline{bb'} = \emptyset = \overline{bb'} \cap \overline{cc'})) \Rightarrow (\overline{aa'} \parallel \overline{cc'}).$

3. VECTORS AND FUNCTIONAL VECTORS

Definition 3.1. For points x, y of an affine space X , the equivalence class

$$\overrightarrow{xy} := \{uv \in X^2 : uv \# xy\}$$

is called the *vector* determined by the pair xy .

The set of all vectors in an affine space X is denoted by $X_{\#}^2$. Therefore,

$$X_{\#}^2 := \{\overrightarrow{xy} : xy \in X\}.$$

Definition 3.2. A vector $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$ in an affine space X is called a *functional vector* if \vec{v} is a function, i.e., for every point $x \in X$ there exists a unique point $y \in X$ such that $xy \in \vec{v}$.

The set of all functional vectors in an affine space X is denoted by \overrightarrow{X} . Definition 2.5 implies the following characterization of functional vectors.

Proposition 3.3 ([2, 14.3.3]). *A vector $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$ in an affine space X is functional if and only if every pair $xy \in \vec{v}$ is Thalesian if and only if some pair $xy \in \vec{v}$ is Thalesian.*

Corollary 2.7 implies the following characterization of Thalesian affine spaces.

Corollary 3.4 ([2, 14.3.4]). *For an affine space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *the affine space X is Thalesian;*
- (2) *every vector in X is functional;*
- (3) $\overrightarrow{X} = X_{\#}^2$;
- (4) *for every point $x \in X$ and vector $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$, there exists a unique point $y \in X$ such that $\vec{v} = \overrightarrow{xy}$.*

The set of functional vectors \overrightarrow{X} contains the distinguished element

$$\vec{0} := \{xx : x \in X\},$$

called the *zero vector*.

The set $X_{\#}^2$ of vectors admits a natural unary operation

$$- : X_{\#}^2 \rightarrow X_{\#}^2, \quad - : \vec{v} \mapsto -\vec{v} := \{yx : xy \in \vec{v}\}.$$

The vector $-\vec{v} = \{\overrightarrow{yx} : xy \in \vec{v}\}$ is called the *opposite vector* to the vector \vec{v} . Proposition 2.2(4) implies that this operation is well-defined. It is clear that $-\vec{0} = \vec{0}$, and the operation of taking the opposite vector is involutive in the sense that $-(-\vec{v}) = \vec{v}$ for every vector $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$. Proposition 2.8 implies that for every functional vector $\vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}$, its opposite vector $-\vec{v}$ is a functional vector. So, the operation of taking the opposite vector is also an unary operation on the set of functional vectors \overrightarrow{X} .

Proposition 3.5 ([2, 14.3.6]). *Let x, y, u, v be points of an affine space X . If $\overrightarrow{xy} = \overrightarrow{uv}$ (and $\overrightarrow{yx} = \overrightarrow{vu} \in \overrightarrow{X}$), then $\overline{xy} \parallel \overline{uv}$ (and $\overline{yx} \parallel \overline{vu}$).*

Proposition 3.6 ([2, 14.3.7]). *Let p, q, u, v be points in an affine space X . If $\overline{pu} \parallel \overline{qv}$ and $\overline{pq} \cap \overline{uv} = \emptyset$, then $\overrightarrow{pq} = \overrightarrow{uv}$.*

Remark 3.7. For every point o in an affine space, the function

$$\vec{X} \rightarrow X, \quad \vec{o}\vec{x} \mapsto x,$$

is well-defined and injective, and the function

$$X \rightarrow X_{\#}^2, \quad x \mapsto \vec{o}\vec{x},$$

is surjective. For a point $x \in X$, the vector $\vec{o}\vec{x}$ is called *the radius-vector* of the point x .

Observe that every vector \vec{v} in an affine space X is the set of pairs $xy \in X^2$. Every pair $xy = \{(0, x), (1, y)\} \in X^2$ can be canonically identified with the ordered pair $(x, y) \in X \times X$, which allows us to think of vectors as relations (which are sets of ordered pairs). The definition of a functional vector implies that for every $x \in X$ there exists a unique point $y \in X$ such that $xy \in \vec{v}$, which means that \vec{v} is a well-defined function, assigning to every point $x \in X$ the unique point $y \in X$ such that $xy \in \vec{v}$. Therefore, it is legal to think of vectors as functions from X to X . It turns out that such functions are exactly translations of X .

Theorem 3.8 ([2, 14.4.1]). *The equality $\vec{X} = \text{Tra}(X)$ holds for every affine space X .*

Remark 3.9. Theorem 3.8 is related to an old discussion about the nature of vectors. Are vectors equivalence classes of directed segments or translations? Theorem 3.8 shows that functional vectors are simultaneously translations and equivalence classes of directed segments. This dual nature of functional vectors can be considered as a geometric counterpart of the famous wave–particle duality in quantum mechanics.

4. THE ADDITION OF FUNCTIONAL VECTORS

Since $\vec{X} = \text{Tra}(X)$, the algebraic structure on the group of translations $\text{Tra}(X)$ can be used to define an operation of addition of functional vectors.

Theorem 4.1 ([2, 14.5.1]). *Let X be an affine space. There exists a unique binary operation*

$$+ : \vec{X} \times \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{X}, \quad + : (\vec{x}, \vec{y}) \mapsto \vec{x} + \vec{y},$$

such that $\vec{x}\vec{y} + \vec{y}\vec{z} = \vec{x}\vec{z}$ for every points $x, y, z \in X$ with $\vec{x}\vec{y}, \vec{y}\vec{z} \in \vec{X}$. The binary operation $+$ has the following properties for every functional vectors $\vec{x}, \vec{y}, \vec{z} \in \vec{X}$:

- (1) $\vec{x} + \vec{y} = \vec{y} \circ \vec{x}$;
- (2) $(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) + \vec{z} = \vec{x} + (\vec{y} + \vec{z})$;
- (3) $\vec{x} + \vec{0} = \vec{x} = \vec{0} + \vec{x}$;
- (4) $\vec{x} + (-\vec{x}) = (-\vec{x}) + \vec{x}$.

Therefore, $(\vec{X}, +)$ is a group with neutral element $\vec{0}$. If for some point $o \in X$, the set $\vec{X}(o) := \{\vec{v}(o) : \vec{v} \in \vec{X}\}$ has rank $\|\vec{X}(o)\| \neq 2$, then the group $(\vec{X}, +)$ is commutative.

Corollary 4.2 ([2, 14.5.2]). *For every Thalesian affine space X , the vector addition has the following properties for every vectors $\vec{x}, \vec{y}, \vec{z} \in \vec{X}$:*

- (1) $\vec{x} + \vec{y} = \vec{y} + \vec{x} = \vec{y} \circ \vec{x}$;
- (2) $(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) + \vec{z} = \vec{x} + (\vec{y} + \vec{z})$;
- (3) $\vec{x} + \vec{0} = \vec{x} = \vec{0} + \vec{x}$;
- (4) $\vec{x} + (-\vec{x}) = \vec{0} = (-\vec{x}) + \vec{x}$.

Therefore, $(\vec{X}, +) = (X_{\#}^2, +)$ is a commutative group.

Corollary 4.3 ([2, 14.5.3]). *Let a, b, x, y be points in a Thalesian affine space X . If $\vec{a}\vec{b} = \vec{x}\vec{y} \in \vec{X}$, then $\vec{a}\vec{x} = \vec{b}\vec{y}$.*

Theorem 4.1 also implies the following properties of the natural action of the group \vec{X} of functional vectors on the affine space X .

Corollary 4.4 ([2, 14.5.4]). *For every affine space X , the map*

$$+ : X \times \overrightarrow{X} \rightarrow X, \quad + : (x, \vec{v}) \mapsto x + \vec{v} := \vec{v}(x),$$

has the following properties:

- (1) $\forall x, y \in X \quad (x + \overrightarrow{xy} = y)$;
- (2) $\forall x \in X \quad (x + \vec{0} = x)$;
- (3) $\forall x \in X \quad \forall \vec{y}, \vec{z} \in \overrightarrow{X} \quad (x + (\vec{y} + \vec{z}) = (x + \vec{y}) + \vec{z})$.

Question 4.5 ([2, 14.5.5]). *Let \vec{v} be a functional vector in an affine space X and ab, xy be two translation equivalent pairs in X . Let $b' := \vec{v}(b)$ and $y' := \vec{v}(y)$. Are the pairs ab' and xy' translation equivalent?*

5. THE SUBPARALLELITY OF VECTORS TO FLATS

Definition 5.1. Let X be an affine space. Given a vector $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$ and a flat $A \subseteq X$, we write $\vec{v} \parallel A$ and say that \vec{v} is *subparallel* to A if $\forall xy \in \vec{v} \quad \overline{xy} \parallel A$.

Proposition 5.2 ([2, 14.6.2]). *A vector \vec{v} in a proaffine space X is subparallel to a flat $A \subseteq X$ if and only if there exist a pair $xy \in \vec{v}$ such that $\overline{xy} \parallel A$.*

Proposition 5.3 ([2, 14.6.3]). *Let A be a flat in a Thalesian affine space X , and $\vec{u}, \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}$ be two functional vectors. If $\vec{u} \parallel A$ and $\vec{v} \parallel A$, then $(\vec{v} + \vec{u}) \parallel A$.*

Corollary 5.4 ([2, 14.6.4]). *Let A be a flat in a Thalesian affine space X and let $o, x, y, z \in X$ be points such that $\overrightarrow{ox} + \overrightarrow{oy} = \overrightarrow{oz}$. If $o, x, y \in A$, then $z \in A$.*

Proposition 5.3 implies that line affinities in Thalesian affine spaces preserve the operation of addition of vectors.

Theorem 5.5 ([2, 14.6.5]). *Let $A : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ be a line affinity between two lines L, Λ in a Thalesian affine space, o, x, y, z be points in the line L and $o', x', y', z' \in \Lambda$ be their images under the function A , respectively. If $\overrightarrow{ox} + \overrightarrow{oy} = \overrightarrow{oz}$, then $\overrightarrow{o'x'} + \overrightarrow{o'y'} = \overrightarrow{o'z'}$.*

Definition 5.6. Given two vectors $\vec{v}, \vec{u} \in \overrightarrow{X}$ in an affine space X we write $\vec{v} \parallel \vec{u}$ (resp. $\vec{v} \parallel \vec{u}$) and say that the vector \vec{v} is *subparallel* (resp. *parallel*) to the vector \vec{u} if $\overline{xv} \parallel \overline{yu}$ (resp. $\overline{xv} \parallel \overline{yu}$) for all pairs $xv \in \vec{v}$ and $yu \in \vec{u}$.

Proposition 5.7 ([2, 14.6.7]). *Let X be an affine space. A vectors $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$ is (sub)parallel to a vector $\vec{u} \in X_{\#}^2$ if and only if the flat \overline{xv} is (sub)parallel to the flat \overline{yu} for some pairs $xv \in \vec{v}$ and $yu \in \vec{u}$.*

6. TRANSFORMATION GROUPS PRESERVING VECTORS

The notion of subparallelity of vectors allows us to define a natural structure of a liner on the group of functional vectors \overrightarrow{X} in an affine space X . Given any distinct functional vectors $\vec{u}, \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}$, consider the set $\overline{\vec{u}\vec{v}} := \{\vec{x} \in \overrightarrow{X} : \vec{x} - \vec{u} \parallel \vec{v} - \vec{u}\}$. It can be shown that the set of functional vectors $\overrightarrow{X} = \text{Tra}(X)$ endowed with the family of lines $\overline{\vec{u}\vec{v}} : \vec{u}, \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}^3, \vec{u} \neq \vec{v}$ is a liner.

Remark 6.1. For every point o in an affine space X , the function $\overrightarrow{X} \rightarrow X, \vec{v} \rightarrow \vec{v}(o)$, is an isomorphism of the liner $(\overrightarrow{X}, \overline{\vec{u}\vec{v}})$ onto the subliner $\overrightarrow{X}(o) := \{\vec{v}(o) : \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}\}$ of the affine space X . The liner \overrightarrow{X} has rank $\|\overrightarrow{X}\| \geq 3$ if and only if $\|\overrightarrow{X}(o)\| \geq 3$. The liner \overrightarrow{X} can have quite intricate geometry. For example, there exists an affine plane X of order 16 for which the liner \overrightarrow{X} has 32 points and contains four parallel lines of length 8, 32 lines of length 4 and 256 lines of length 2.

Next, we consider three transformation groups on an affine space X , which coincide with the group of translations $\text{Tra}(X)$, if the affine space X is Thalesian. Those transformation groups consist of linevections, vections and funvections, respectively.

Definition 6.2. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X is defined to be

- a *linevection* if for every line $L \subset X$, the restriction $A|_L$ is a line translation;
- a *vection* if $Axy \# xy$ for every pair $xy \in X^2$;
- a *funvection* if $Axy \# xy$ for every Thalesian pair $xy \in X^2$.

Proposition 6.3 ([2, 14.7.5]). *Let $A : X \rightarrow X$ be an automorphism of an affine space X .*

- (1) *If A is a linevection, then A is a vection;*
- (2) *If A is a vection, then A is a funvection;*
- (3) *If A is a vection, then A is a dilation;*
- (4) *A is a funvection if and only if $AT = TA$ for every translation $T \in \text{Tra}(X)$.*
- (5) *If $\|\vec{X}\| \neq 0$ and A is a funvection and a dilation, then A is a translation.*
- (6) *If A is a translation and $\|\vec{X}\| \neq 2$, then A is a linevection.*
- (7) *If $\|\vec{X}\| \geq 3$, then A is a translation if and only if A is a linevection if and only if it is a vection if and only if A is a funvection and a dilation.*
- (8) *If $X = \bigcup_{T \in \text{Tra}(X)} \overline{\{o, T(o)\}}$ for some $o \in X$ and A is a funvection, then A is a dilation.*

For an affine space X , let $\text{Tra}_L(X)$, $\text{Tra}_V(X)$, and $\text{Tra}_F(X)$ denote the subsets of the group $\text{Aut}(X)$, consisting of linevections, vections, and funvections, respectively. It is easy to see that $\text{Tra}_L(X)$, $\text{Tra}_V(X)$ and $\text{Tra}_F(X)$ are normal subgroups of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$. Proposition 6.3 implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tra}_L(X) &\subseteq \text{Tra}_V(X) \subseteq \text{Tra}_F(X) \cap \text{Dil}(X) \quad \text{and} \\ \text{Tra}_F(X) &= \mathcal{Z}(\text{Tra}(X)) := \{A \in \text{Aut}(X) : \forall T \in \text{Tra}(X), TA = AT\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 6.3 also implies the following corollaries.

Corollary 6.4 ([2, 14.7.6]). *Let X be an affine space such that $\|\vec{X}\| \geq 3$. Then*

$$\vec{X} = \text{Tra}(X) = \text{Tra}_L(X) = \text{Tra}_V(X) = \text{Tra}_F(X) \cap \text{Dil}(X) \subseteq \text{Tra}_F(X) = \mathcal{Z}(\text{Tra}(X)).$$

Corollary 6.5 ([2, 14.7.7]). *Let X be an affine space such that $X = \bigcup_{T \in \text{Tra}(X)} \overline{\{o, T(o)\}}$ for some $o \in X$. Then $\vec{X} = \text{Tra}(X) = \text{Tra}_L(X) = \text{Tra}_V(X) = \text{Tra}_F(X) = \mathcal{Z}(\text{Tra}(X))$.*

Corollary 6.6 ([2, 14.7.8]). *If an affine space X is Thalesian, then $\vec{X} = \text{Tra}(X) = \text{Tra}_L(X) = \text{Tra}_V(X) = \text{Tra}_F(X) = \mathcal{Z}(\text{Tra}(X))$.*

Remark 6.7 ([2, 14.7.9]). For non-Thalesian affine planes the groups $\text{Tra}(X)$, $\text{Tra}_L(X)$, $\text{Tra}_V(X)$, $\text{Tra}_F(X)$ can be distinct, as shown in the following table of cardinalities of those groups for all seven (pairwise nonisomorphic) affine planes of order 9.

X	$\ \vec{X}\ $	$\text{Tra}(X)$	$\text{Tra}_L(X)$	$\text{Tra}_V(X)$	$\text{Tra}_F(X)$	$\text{Dil}(X)$	$\text{Aut}(X)$	$\text{Aut}(\vec{X})$
Desarg	3	81	81	81	81	648	933120	84913920
Thales	3	81	81	81	81	162	311040	311040
Hall	2	9	9	9	9	72	311040	311040
Hughes	3	9	9	9	9	18	2592	33696
dhall	1	1	?	8	3456	8	3456	311040
hall	1	1	?	2	3840	2	3840	311040
hughes	1	1	1	1	432	1	432	33696

7. AFFINE EQUIVALENCE OF LINE TRIPLES IN AFFINE SPACES

In this section we discuss the notion of affine equivalence of line triples in an affine space X . Every triple $x_0x_1x_2 \in X^3$ is (by definition) the function $\{(0, x_0), (1, x_1), (2, x_2)\} : 3 \rightarrow X$ on the number $3 := \{0, 1, 2\}$. So, for any function F , we can consider the composition

$$Fx_0x_1x_2 := \{(i, F(x_i)) : i \in 3, x_i \in \text{dom}[F]\}$$

of the functions $x_0x_1x_2$ and F . The function $Fx_0x_1x_2$ has domain $\text{dom}[Fx_0x_1x_2] = \{i \in 3 : x_i \in \text{dom}[F]\}$. This domain equals 3 if and only if $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\} \subseteq \text{dom}[F]$.

A triple $xyz \in X^3$ in a liner X is called a *line triple* if $x \neq z$ and $y \in \overline{xz}$. Let \vec{X} denote the set of all line triples in a liner X .

Definition 7.1. Let X be an affine space. Given two line triples abc, xyz in X , we write $abc \bowtie xyz$ and say that abc and xyz are *affinely equivalent* if there exists a line affinity A in X such that $Aabc = xyz$.

Proposition 7.2 ([2, 16.1.2]). *Let X be an affine space. For any line triples abc, uvw, xyz in X , the following properties hold:*

- (1) $abc \bowtie abc$;
- (2) $abc \bowtie uvw \Leftrightarrow uvw \bowtie abc$;
- (3) $(abc \bowtie uvw \wedge uvw \bowtie xyz) \Rightarrow abc \bowtie xyz$;
- (4) $abc \bowtie uvw \Leftrightarrow cba \bowtie wvu$;
- (5) $aac \bowtie uuv \wedge acc \bowtie uuv$;
- (6) *If $abc \bowtie uvw$, then $(a = b \Leftrightarrow u = v) \wedge (b = c \Leftrightarrow v = w)$.*

In the following theorem we characterize the affine equivalence without mentioning line affinities.

Theorem 7.3 ([2, 16.1.4]). *Two line triples abc, uvw in a (Desarguesian) affine space X are affinely equivalent if and only if there exist a number $n \in \omega$ (with $n \leq 2$), line triples $x_0y_0z_0, x_1y_1z_1, \dots, x_ny_nz_n$, and lines $\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_n$ such that $x_0y_0z_0 = abc$, $x_ny_nz_n = uvw$, and $\overline{x_{i-1}x_i} \parallel \Lambda_i$, $\overline{y_{i-1}y_i} \parallel \Lambda_i$, $\overline{z_{i-1}z_i} \parallel \Lambda_i$, $\overline{x_{i-1}z_{i-1}} \neq \overline{x_i z_i}$ for all positive $i \leq n$.*

8. DESARGUESIAN TRIPLES IN AFFINE SPACES

Proposition 8.1 ([2, 16.2.1]). *For every line triple abc in an affine space X and every distinct points x, z in X there exists a point $y \in \overline{xz}$ such that $abc \bowtie xyz$.*

Theorem 8.2 ([2, 16.2.2]). *An affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if for every line triple abc in X and every distinct points $x, z \in X$ there exists a unique point $y \in \overline{xz}$ such that $xyz \bowtie abc$.*

Proposition 8.2 motivates the following definition.

Definition 8.3. A line triple abc in an affine space X is *Desarguesian* if for every distinct points $x, z \in X$, there exists a unique point $y \in \overline{xz}$ such that $xyz \bowtie abc$.

Proposition 7.2(5) implies the following important example of Desarguesian line triples.

Example 8.4. For every distinct points a, c in an affine space X , the line triples aac and acc are Desarguesian.

In terms of Desarguesian triples, Theorem 8.2 can be rewritten as follows.

Theorem 8.5 ([2, 16.2.5]). *An affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if every line triple in X is Desarguesian.*

Proposition 8.6 ([2, 16.2.6]). *A line triple abc in an affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if $A(b) = b$ for any line affinity A with $Aac = ac$.*

Proposition 8.7 ([2, 16.2.7]). *Let a, b, c, d be four points in an affine space X .*

- (1) *If the triple abc is Desarguesian, then the triple cba is Desarguesian;*
- (2) *If the triple abc is Desarguesian and $a \neq b$, then the triple acb is Desarguesian.*
- (3) *If the triples abc and acd are Desarguesian, then the triple abd is Desarguesian.*

9. PORTIONS AND SCALARS IN AFFINE SPACES

Let \ddot{X} denote the set $\{xyz \in X^3 : y \in \overline{xz} \wedge x \neq z\}$ of all line triples in a liner X .

Definition 9.1. For a line triple $zvu \in \ddot{X}$ in an affine space X , its equivalence class

$$\overrightarrow{zvu} := \{abc \in \ddot{X} : abc \bowtie zvu\}$$

is called the *portion* determined by the line triple zvu . The portion \overrightarrow{zvu} will be also denoted by zv/zu and called the *ratio* of the pairs zv and zu .

The portion \overrightarrow{zvu} is called a *scalar* if the line triple zvu is Desarguesian. In this case every line triple $abc \in \overrightarrow{zvu}$ is Desarguesian.

In a line triple zvu , the points z, v, u play non-symmetric roles. The notations z, v, u are abbreviations of *zero*, *variable*, *unit*, respectively.

For an affine space X , let $\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} := \{\overrightarrow{zvu} : zvu \in \ddot{X}\}$ be the set of all portions in the affine space X , and let \mathbb{R}_X be the set of scalars in X , i.e., the set of portions $\overrightarrow{zvu} \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$ (or ratios zv/zu) of Desarguesian line triples zvu in X . Therefore, $\mathbb{R}_X \subseteq \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$. By Theorem 8.5, an affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if $\mathbb{R}_X = \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$.

For every affine space X , the set \mathbb{R}_X contains two important scalars

$$0 := \{xyz \in X^3 : x = y \neq z\} \quad \text{and} \quad 1 := \{xyz \in X^3 : x \neq y = z\}.$$

Proposition 7.2(8) implies that 0 and 1 are indeed scalars, which can be characterized as follows.

Proposition 9.2 ([2, 16.3.2]). *For a line triple zvu in an affine space X*

- (1) $\overrightarrow{zvu} = 0$ if and only if $v = z$;
- (2) $\overrightarrow{zvu} = 1$ if and only if $v = u$.

In the sets $\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$ and \mathbb{R}_X , consider two important subsets

$$\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}^* := \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \setminus \{0\} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{R}_X^* := \mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{0\}$$

of nonzero portions and scalars, respectively.

10. UNARY OPERATIONS ON PORTIONS

In this section we consider two natural unary operations on portions, which are induced by permutations of line triples. The permutation $zvu \mapsto zuv$ induces the operation of inversion of nonzero portions.

Proposition 10.1 ([2, 16.4.1]). *For every affine space X , there exists a unique unary operation*

$$(\cdot)^{-1} : \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}, \quad (\cdot)^{-1} : \alpha \mapsto \alpha^{-1},$$

such that $(\overrightarrow{zvu})^{-1} = \overrightarrow{zuv}$ for every line triple $zvu \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$ with $v \neq z$.

Definition 10.2. The unary operation $(\cdot)^{-1}$ on $\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}^*$ (resp. \mathbb{R}_X) introduced in Proposition 10.1 will be called the *operation of inversion* of portions (resp. scalars) in the affine space X .

Propositions 10.1 and 8.7(2) imply the following corollary.

Corollary 10.3 ([2, 16.4.3]). *Let X be an affine space. The operation of inversion on the set $\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}^*$ has the following properties:*

- (1) $(p^{-1})^{-1} = p$ for every $p \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}^*$;
- (2) for every nonzero scalar $p \in \mathbb{R}_X^*$ its inverse p^{-1} is a nonzero scalar.

By Corollary 10.3(2), the operation of inversion is an involution¹ on the sets $\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}^*$ and \mathbb{R}_X^* . Proposition 7.2(4) implies that the following proposition.

Proposition 10.4 ([2, 16.4.5]). *For every affine space X , there exists a unique unary operation*

$$1- : \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}, \quad 1- : p \mapsto 1-p,$$

such that $1-\overrightarrow{zvu} = \overrightarrow{uvz}$ for every line triple $zvu \in \ddot{X}$.

The unary operation $1- : \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$, introduced in Proposition 10.4 is called the *01-involution* of the set of portions in the affine space X .

Proposition 10.5 ([2, 16.4.6]). *The 01-involution on an affine space X has following properties:*

- (1) $1-(1-p) = p$ for every portion $p \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$;
- (2) $1-0 = 1$ and $1-1 = 0$;
- (3) for every scalar $p \in \mathbb{R}_X$, the portion $1-p$ is a scalar.

¹A self-map $F : X \rightarrow X$ of a set X is called an *involution* if $F(F(x)) = x$ for every $x \in X$.

11. SCALING VECTORS BY SCALARS

The importance of scalars for affine geometry is explained by the fact that the set of scalars \mathbb{R}_X admits a natural action on the set X^2 or pairs, which allows to “scale distances”. This action is the function $\mathbb{R}_X \times X^2 \rightarrow X^2$ assigning to every scalar $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_X$ and pair $xz \in X^2$ the pair xy , where $y \in \overline{xz}$ is a unique point such that $xyz \in \{xxx\} \cup \sigma$.

What is even more important is that this action of \mathbb{R}_X on X^2 induces an action of \mathbb{R}_X on the set of vectors $X_{\#}^2$, which allows one to scale vectors in an affine space X .

Theorem 11.1 ([2, 16.5.1]). *For every affine space X , there exists a unique function*

$$\cdot : \mathbb{R}_X \times X_{\#}^2 \rightarrow X_{\#}^2, \quad (\sigma, \vec{v}) \mapsto \sigma \cdot \vec{v}$$

such that for every scalar $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_X$ and triple $xyz \in X^3$ with $xyz \in \{xxx\} \cup \sigma$ we have $\sigma \cdot \overrightarrow{xz} = \overrightarrow{xy}$.

Proposition 11.2 ([2, 16.5.2]). *Let X be an affine space. For every scalar $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_X$ and vector $\vec{v} \in X_{\#}^2$, the following properties hold;*

- (1) $\sigma \cdot \vec{0} = \vec{0}$;
- (2) $0 \cdot \vec{v} = \vec{0}$;
- (3) $1 \cdot \vec{v} = \vec{v}$;
- (4) *If $\vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}$, then $\sigma \cdot \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X}$.*

12. MULTIPLICATION OF SCALARS AND PORTIONS

Scalars also can scale portions, which leads to the operation of multiplication of scalars and portions.

Theorem 12.1. *For every affine space X , there exists a unique binary operation*

$$\cdot : \text{dom}[\cdot] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X, \quad \cdot : (\alpha, \beta) \mapsto \alpha \cdot \beta, \quad \text{on the set } \text{dom}[\cdot] := (\mathbb{R}_X \times \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}) \cup (\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \times \mathbb{R}_X)$$

such that for every pair of nonzero portions $(\alpha, \beta) \in \text{dom}[\cdot]$ the following two conditions are satisfied:

- (1) *if $\beta = 0$, then $\alpha \cdot \beta = 0$;*
- (2) $\forall o, x, y, u \in X \ (oxy \in \alpha \wedge oyu \in \beta) \Rightarrow (\overrightarrow{oxy} \cdot \overrightarrow{oyu} = \overrightarrow{oxu})$.

Definition 12.2. The operation $\cdot : \text{dom}[\cdot] \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$ defined in Theorem 12.1 is called the *operation of multiplication of scalars and portions* in X .

Theorem 12.3 ([2, 16.6.1]). *For every affine space X , the multiplication of scalars by portions has the following properties:*

- (1) $\forall \alpha \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \ (\alpha \cdot 0 = 0 = 0 \cdot \alpha)$;
- (2) $\forall \alpha \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \ (\alpha \cdot 1 = \alpha = 1 \cdot \alpha)$;
- (3) $\forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_X^* \ (\alpha \cdot \alpha^{-1} = 1 = \alpha^{-1} \cdot \alpha)$;
- (4) $\forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X \ (\alpha \cdot \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X)$;
- (5) $\forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X \ \forall \gamma \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \ (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot \gamma = \alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot \gamma)$;
- (6) $\forall \alpha \in \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} \ \forall \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_X \ (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot \gamma = \alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot \gamma)$.

Remark 12.4. Theorem 12.3 implies that for every affine space X , the set of scalars \mathbb{R}_X endowed with the operation of multiplication of scalars is a monoid with zero, and \mathbb{R}_X^* is a subgroup of this monoid.

Finally, we show that the actions of the monoid \mathbb{R}_X on the sets X^2 and $X_{\#}^2$ agree with the algebraic structure of the monoid \mathbb{R}_X .

Theorem 12.5 ([2, 16.6.5]). *For every points $x, y \in X$ in an affine space X and every scalars $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X$, the following equalities hold:*

- (1) $\alpha \cdot xx = xx$ and $\alpha \cdot \vec{0} = \vec{0}$;
- (2) $0 \cdot xy = xx$ and $0 \cdot \overrightarrow{xy} = \vec{0}$;
- (3) $1 \cdot xy = xy$ and $1 \cdot \overrightarrow{xy} = \overrightarrow{xy}$;
- (4) $\alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot xy) = (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot xy$ and $\alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot \overrightarrow{xy}) = (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot \overrightarrow{xy}$.

13. THE COMMUTATIVITY OF MULTIPLICATION OF SCALARS

Lemma 13.1 ([2, 16.7.1]). *Let X be an affine space. For any scalars $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $\alpha \cdot \beta = \beta \cdot \alpha$;
- (2) *for any concurrent lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$ and $o \in L \cap L'$ with $oab \in \alpha$ and $ocb \in \beta$, the parallelity relations $\overline{ab} \parallel \overline{a'b'}$ and $\overline{bc} \parallel \overline{b'c'}$ imply $\overline{ac} \parallel \overline{a'c'}$.*

Lemma 13.1 implies the following characterization of affine spaces with commutative monoid of scalars.

Theorem 13.2 ([2, 16.7.2]). *For an affine space X , the multiplicative monoid of scalars \mathbb{R}_X is commutative if and only if for every concurrent lines $L, L' \subseteq X$ and points $a, b, c \in L \setminus L'$, $a', b', c' \in L' \setminus L$ and $o \in L \cap L'$, if $\overline{a'b} \parallel \overline{ab'}$, $\overline{bc'} \parallel \overline{b'c}$, and the line triples oba , ocb are Desarguesian, then $\overline{ac'} \parallel \overline{a'c}$.*

14. SCALARS AND HOMOTHETIES IN AFFINE SPACES

In this section we study the interplay between scalars and homotheties of (Thalesian) affine spaces. Let us recall that a *homothety* is a dilation possessing a fixed point. For every point o in an affine space X , the set $\text{Dil}_o(X) := \{D \in \text{Dil}(X) : D(o) = o\}$ is a subgroup of the dilation group $\text{Dil}(X)$ of the affine space X . If the affine space X is Thalesian, then group $\text{Dil}_o(X)$ is isomorphic to the quotient group $\text{Dil}(X)/\text{Tra}(X)$, by [2, 12.3.7].

Let $\mathbb{R}_X^* = \mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{0\}$ be the multiplicative group of non-zero scalars in an affine space X .

Given a nonzero scalar $s \in \mathbb{R}_X^*$ and a point $o \in X$, consider the function $s_o : X \rightarrow X$ assigning to every point $x \in X$ the unique point $y \in X$ such that $oyx \in s \cup \{ooo\}$.

Proposition 14.1 ([2, 16.8.1]). *For every point o in an affine space X and every scalar $s \in \mathbb{R}_X^*$, the function $s_o : X \rightarrow X$ is a homothety of X with $s_o(o) = o$.*

Theorem 14.2 ([2, 16.8.2]). *For every point o in an affine space X , the function*

$$*_o : \mathbb{R}_X^* \rightarrow \text{Dil}_o(X), \quad *_o : s \mapsto s_o,$$

*is an injective group homomorphism. If the affine space X is Thalesian, then the function $*_o : \mathbb{R}_X^* \rightarrow \text{Dil}_o(X)$ is a group isomorphism and hence the groups \mathbb{R}_X^* and $\text{Dil}(X)/\text{Tra}(X)$ are isomorphic.*

Corollary 14.3 ([2, 16.8.3]). *For every Thalesian affine space X , the group of dilations $\text{Dil}(X)$ is a semidirect product $\overrightarrow{X} \rtimes \mathbb{R}_X^*$ of the groups $(\overrightarrow{X}, +)$ and (\mathbb{R}_X^*, \cdot) .*

Theorem 14.4 ([2, 16.8.4]). *Let X be an affine space. If $\mathbb{R}_X \neq \{0, 1\}$, then X is Thalesian.*

15. SCALARS IN THALESIAN AFFINE SPACES

By Theorem 14.4, every affine space X with $\mathbb{R}_X \neq \{0, 1\}$ is Thalesian. In this section we shall establish that for any Thalesian affine space X its set of scalars \mathbb{R}_X has a natural addition operation turning the monoid \mathbb{R}_X into a corps (= skew-field).

By Corollary 3.4, every vector in a Thalesian affine space X is functional, and by Corollary 4.2, the set $\overrightarrow{X} = X_{\#}^2$ of (functional) vectors in X is a commutative group with respect to the operation of addition. We shall use this operation of vector addition for defining the operation of addition of scalars in Thalesian affine spaces.

Theorem 15.1 ([2, 16.9.1]). *For every Thalesian affine space X , there exists a unique binary operation $+$: $\mathbb{R}_X \times \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$, $+$: $(\alpha, \beta) \mapsto \alpha + \beta$, such that for every distinct points $o, e \in X$ and points $x, y, z \in \overline{oe}$ with $\overrightarrow{ox} + \overrightarrow{oy} = \overrightarrow{oz}$, we have $\overrightarrow{oxe} + \overrightarrow{oye} = \overrightarrow{oze}$.*

Theorem 15.2 ([2, 16.9.2+16.9.3]). *For every Thalesian affine space X , the addition of scalars has the following properties:*

- (1) **Associativity:** $\forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad (\alpha + \beta) + \gamma = \alpha + (\beta + \gamma)$;

- (2) **Commutativity:** $\forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \alpha + \beta = \beta + \alpha$;
- (3) **Zero:** $\forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \alpha + 0 = \alpha$;
- (4) **Invertibility:** $\forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \exists \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \alpha + \beta = 0$;
- (5) **Left Distributivity:** $\forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \alpha \cdot (\beta + \gamma) = \alpha \cdot \beta + \alpha \cdot \gamma$;
- (6) **Right Distributivity:** $\forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad (\alpha + \beta) \cdot \gamma = \alpha \cdot \gamma + \beta \cdot \gamma$.

Theorem 15.2 motivates the following definition.

Definition 15.3. A *corps* is a set F endowed with two binary operations $+, \cdot : F \times F \rightarrow F$ and two distinct elements $0, 1 \in F$ satisfying the following axioms:

- (1) $\forall x, y, z \in F \quad x + (y + z) = (x + y) + z$;
- (2) $\forall x, y \in F \quad x + y = y + x$;
- (3) $\forall x \in F \quad x + 0 = x = 0 + x$;
- (4) $\forall x \in F \quad \exists y \in F \quad x + y = 0 = y + x$;
- (5) $\forall x, y, z \in F \quad x \cdot (y \cdot z) = (x \cdot y) \cdot z$;
- (6) $\forall x \in F \quad x \cdot 1 = x = 1 \cdot x$;
- (7) $\forall x \in F \setminus \{0\} \quad \exists y \in F \quad x \cdot y = 1 = y \cdot x$;
- (8) $\forall a, x, y \in F \quad a \cdot (x + y) = a \cdot x + a \cdot y$;
- (9) $\forall a, x, y \in F \quad (x + y) \cdot a = x \cdot a + y \cdot a$.

A corps F is called a *field* if $x \cdot y = y \cdot x$ for all $x, y \in F$.

Theorem 15.4 ([2, 16.9.9]). *The addition operation of a corps R is uniquely determined by the operations of multiplication and 01-involution $1- : R \rightarrow R, 1- : x \mapsto 1 - x$.*

Theorems 12.3 and 15.2 imply

Theorem 15.5 ([2, 16.9.10]). *For every Thalesian affine space X , its set of scalars \mathbb{R}_X is a corps with respect to the operations of addition and multiplication of scalars.*

By Theorem 15.4, the operation of addition of scalars in a Thalesian affine space is uniquely determined by the operations of scalar multiplication and the involution $1- : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X, 1- : s \mapsto 1 - s$. The following theorem shows that this involution agrees with the operation of 01-involution $1- : X_{\#}^2 \rightarrow X_{\#}^2, 1- : \overrightarrow{zvu} \mapsto \overrightarrow{uvz}$, introduced in Section 10.

Theorem 15.6 ([2, 16.9.11]). *For every Desarguesian triple xyz in an affine space X , we have the equality $\overrightarrow{xy\dot{z}} + \overrightarrow{zy\dot{x}} = \overrightarrow{xz\dot{z}} = 1$, which implies $1-s = 1 - s$ for every scalar $s \in \mathbb{R}_X$.*

16. THE SCALAR CORPUS OF AN AFFINE SPACE

Theorems 15.4 and 15.6 allow us to introduce a canonical structure of a corps on the set of scalars \mathbb{R}_X of any (not necessarily Thalesian) affine space X . This can be done as follows.

Using the operations of multiplication and 01-involution, for every $y \in \mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{1\}$ we can define the opposite scalar $-y$ to y by the formula

$$-y := (1-y) \cdot (1-(1-y)^{-1}),$$

where $(1-y)^{-1}$ is the inverse of the nonzero element $1-y$ in the group \mathbb{R}_X^* . The opposite scalar -1 to 1 is defined as the unique element of the set $\mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{y \cdot (1-y^{-1}) : y \in \mathbb{R}_X^*\}$. The following lemma shows that the element -1 is well-defined.

Lemma 16.1 ([2, 16.10.1]). *For every affine space X , the set $\mathbb{R}_X \setminus \{y \cdot (1-y^{-1}) : y \in \mathbb{R}_X^*\}$ is a singleton.*

Endow \mathbb{R}_X with the binary operation $+ : \mathbb{R}_X \times \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$, assigning to every scalars $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_X$ the scalar

$$(1) \quad x + y := \begin{cases} y & \text{if } x = 0; \\ x \cdot (1 - (x^{-1} \cdot (-y))) & \text{if } x \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

It can be shown that for every Thalesian affine space X , the addition operation defined by the formula (1) coincides with the operation of addition of scalars introduced in Section 15. Because

of that we use the same notation for both operations of addition of scalars on Thalesian affine spaces.

Theorem 16.2 ([2, 16.10.2]). *For every affine space X , the set of scalars \mathbb{R}_X endowed with the operations of addition and multiplication is a corp.*

Definition 16.3. For every affine space X , the corp of scalars \mathbb{R}_X is called the *scalar corp* of the affine space X .

For affine liners X with $|X|_2 = 2$ it is convenient to assume that \mathbb{R}_X is the two-element field $\{0, 1\}$.

17. THE VECTOR SPACE OF A THALESIAN AFFINE SPACE

In this section we shall prove that the set of vectors \vec{X} in a Thalesian affine space X carries a natural structure of a module over the scalar corps \mathbb{R}_X of X .

Definition 17.1. An *R -module* over a corps R is a nonempty set \mathbf{X} endowed with binary operations $+$: $\mathbf{X} \times \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$, $+$: $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \mapsto \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}$, and \cdot : $R \times \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$, \cdot : $(\alpha, \mathbf{x}) \mapsto \alpha \cdot \mathbf{x}$, that satisfy the axioms:

- (1) $\forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{X} \quad (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}) + \mathbf{z} = \mathbf{x} + (\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})$;
- (2) $\forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{X} \quad 0 \cdot \mathbf{x} = 0 \cdot \mathbf{y}$;
- (3) $\forall \alpha, \beta \in R \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X} \quad \alpha \cdot (\beta \cdot \mathbf{x}) = (\alpha \cdot \beta) \cdot \mathbf{x}$;
- (4) $\forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X} \quad 1 \cdot \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}$;
- (5) $\forall \alpha, \beta \in R \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X} \quad (\alpha + \beta) \cdot \mathbf{x} = \alpha \cdot \mathbf{x} + \beta \cdot \mathbf{x}$;
- (6) $\forall \alpha \in R \quad \forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{X} \quad \alpha \cdot (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}) = \alpha \cdot \mathbf{x} + \alpha \cdot \mathbf{y}$.

Modules over fields are also called *vector spaces*.

Remark 17.2. Every R -module \mathbf{X} over a corps R is a commutative group with respect to the addition operation (this follows from the distributivity and associativity of the addition). Moreover, for every $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}$ the element $0 \cdot \mathbf{x}$ is the neutral element of the group $(\mathbf{X}, +)$ and the element $(-1) \cdot \mathbf{x}$ is the inverse element to \mathbf{x} in the group $(\mathbf{X}, +)$.

Theorem 17.3 ([2, 17.1.3]). *For every Thalesian affine space X , its set of vectors \vec{X} endowed with the operations of addition $+$: $\vec{X} \times \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{X}$ and multiplication \cdot : $\mathbb{R}_X \times \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{X}$ is an \mathbb{R}_X -module.*

18. THE ALGEBRAIC STRUCTURE OF LINES AND FLATS IN AFFINE SPACES

In this section we prove that the line structure \mathcal{L} of a Desarguesian affine space X can be recovered from the vector space structure of \vec{X} and the map $\overrightarrow{\ast\ast} : X \rightarrow \vec{X}$, $\overrightarrow{\ast\ast} : (x, y) \mapsto \overrightarrow{xy}$.

Proposition 18.1 ([2, 17.2.1]). *For any distinct points o, e of an affine space X , the line \overline{oe} contains the set $\{x \in X : \exists \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \overrightarrow{ox} = \alpha \cdot \overrightarrow{oe}\}$.*

Theorem 18.2 ([2, 17.2.2]). *A Thalesian affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if for any distinct points $o, e \in X$, the line \overline{oe} coincides with the set $\{x \in X : \exists \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \overrightarrow{ox} = \alpha \cdot \overrightarrow{oe}\}$.*

Remark 18.3. It can be shown that for any points o, u, v in a Desarguesian affine space X , the plane $\overline{\{o, u, v\}}$ coincides with the set $\{x \in X : \exists \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \overrightarrow{ox} = \alpha \cdot \overrightarrow{ou} + \beta \cdot \overrightarrow{ov}\}$.

Definition 18.4. Let \mathbf{Y} be an R -module over a corps R . A subset $\mathbf{X} \subseteq \mathbf{Y}$ is called an *R -submodule* of \mathbf{Y} if it has two properties:

- (1) $\forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{X} \quad (\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{X})$;
- (2) $\forall \alpha \in R \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X} \quad (\alpha \cdot \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X})$.

If R is a field, then an R -submodule \mathbf{X} of an R -module \mathbf{Y} is also called a *vector subspace* of the vector space \mathbf{Y} .

Proposition 18.5 ([2, 17.2.7]). *For every nonempty flat A in a Thalesian affine space X , the set*

$$\vec{A} := \{\vec{x} \in \vec{X} : \vec{x} \parallel A\}$$

is an \mathbb{R}_X -submodule of the \mathbb{R}_X -module \vec{X} .

Theorem 18.6 ([2, 17.2.8]). *A subset A of a Desarguesian affine space X is flat in X if and only if the set $\vec{A} := \{\vec{x} \in \vec{X} : \vec{x} \parallel A\}$ is an \mathbb{R}_X -submodule of the \mathbb{R}_X -module \vec{X} .*

19. THE PRIME FIELD OF AN AFFINE SPACE

A field F is called *prime* if F contains no proper subfields. Every prime field is isomorphic either to the field \mathbb{Q} of rational numbers or to the field $\mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$ of residues modulo a prime number p . Every corps R contains a unique prime subfield, which is the smallest subfield of R that contains 0 and 1. In particular, the scalar corps \mathbb{R}_X of a Thalesian affine space X has a unique prime subfield \mathbb{Q}_X . The structure of the prime field \mathbb{Q}_X depends on the characteristic of the corps \mathbb{R}_X .

Definition 19.1. The *characteristic* of a corps R is the order of the element 1 in the additive group of the corps R .

Since corps have no divisors of zero, the characteristic of a corps is either infinite or a prime number. If a corps R has finite characteristic p , then its prime field coincides with the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\} \subseteq R$ and is isomorphic to the p -element field $\mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$. If R has infinite characteristic, then its prime field coincides with the set of fractions $\{\frac{m}{n} : m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ and is isomorphic to the field of rationals \mathbb{Q} .

For every Thalesian space X , its vector space \vec{X} is an \mathbb{R}_X -module and also a \mathbb{Q}_X -module, so \vec{X} is a vector space over the prime field \mathbb{Q}_X . This fact implies the following important theorem.

Theorem 19.2 ([2, 17.3.2]). *Every finite Thalesian affine space X has order $|X|_2 = p^n$ and cardinality $|X| = p^{n \dim(X)}$ for some prime number p and some number $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If $n = 1$, then the affine space X is Desarguesian.*

Definition 19.3. An affine liner X is defined to be *prime* (resp. *prime-power*) if it has order p (resp. p^k) for some prime number p (and some number $k \in \mathbb{N}$).

Theorem 19.4 ([2, 17.3.4]). *For a prime affine space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) X is Desarguesian;
- (2) X is Thalesian;
- (3) X is translation;
- (4) X is ∂ -translation.

Theorem 19.4 motivates the following old open problem,

Problem 19.5. *Is every prime affine space Desarguesian?*

Theorem 19.2 implies that every finite Thalesian affine space is prime-power. This fact suggests the following old open problem.

Problem 19.6. *Is every finite affine space prime-power?*

20. GEOMETRY OF MODULES OVER CORPS

By Theorem 17.3, every Thalesian affine space X is an \mathbb{R}_X -module over the scalar corps \mathbb{R}_X . This fact motivates studying the geometry of modules over corps in more details. First we present two important examples of R -modules.

Example 20.1 ([2, 18.1.1]). For a corps R and a set B , the set R^B of functions $f : B \rightarrow R$ is an R -module with respect to the operation of addition of functions and left multiplication of functions by elements of the corps R . The subset $R^{\oplus B} := \{f \in R^B : |\text{supp}(f)| < \omega\}$ of finitely supported functions is an R -submodule of the R -module R^B .

For a function $f : B \rightarrow R$ with values in a corps R , its *support* is the set

$$\text{supp}(f) := \{x \in B : f(x) \neq 0\}.$$

Every R -module X over a corps R carries the *canonical line structure*

$$\mathcal{L} := \{x + R \cdot v : x \in X, v \in X \setminus \{\mathbf{0}\}\},$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ is the neutral element of the additive group of the R -module X .

Lemma 20.2 ([2, 18.1.3]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps R and aob be a triangle in the liner X . For every elements $r, s \in R \setminus \{0, 1\}$ and points $x := o + r \cdot (a - o) \in \overline{oa}$ and $y := o + s \cdot (b - o) \in \overline{ob}$, we have $\overline{xy} \cap \overline{ab} = \emptyset$ if and only if $r = s$.*

The following lemma describes the algebraic structure of flats in modules over corps.

Lemma 20.3 ([2, 18.1.4]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps $R \neq \{0, 1\}$. For every nonempty set $A \subseteq X$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *A is flat in the liner X ;*
- (2) *for every $o \in A$, the set $A - o$ is an R -submodule of the R -module;*
- (3) *for some $o \in A$, the set $A - o$ is an R -submodule of the R -module.*

Proposition 20.4 ([2, 18.1.5]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps $R \neq \{0, 1\}$. For every set $B \subseteq X$ its flat hull \overline{B} in the liner X coincides with the set*

$$\Sigma := \{\sum_{b \in B} f(b) \cdot b : f \in R^{\oplus B}, \sum_{b \in B} f(b) = 1\}.$$

Theorem 20.5 ([2, 18.1.8]). *Every R -module over a corps R is a Desarguesian affine regular liner.*

Proposition 20.6 ([2, 18.1.12]). *Let X be an R -module over a corps $R \neq \{0, 1\}$. If $\|X\| \geq 3$, then the corps \mathbb{R}_X of the Desarguesian affine space X is isomorphic to the corps R .*

21. ISOMORPHISMS OF DESARGUESIAN AFFINE SPACES

Since vectors and scalars in an affine space are defined using the line structure of the affine space, those notions are preserved by liner isomorphisms of affine spaces. More precisely, every isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between affine spaces X, Y induces bijective maps $\vec{F} : \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{Y}$ and $\ddot{F} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_Y$ assigning to every vector $\vec{v} \in \vec{X}$ the vector $\vec{F}(\vec{v}) := \{Fxy : xy \in \vec{v}\}$ and to every scalar $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_X$ the scalar $\ddot{F}(\sigma) := \{Fxyz : xyz \in \sigma\}$. The bijection $\vec{F} : \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{Y}$ preserves the zero vectors and the inversion of vectors, and the bijection $\ddot{F} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_Y$ is an isomorphism of the corps \mathbb{R}_X and \mathbb{R}_Y .

The definitions of the operations of addition of vectors, addition and muliplication of scalars, and multiplication of scalars and vectors imply the following proposition.

Proposition 21.1 ([2, 18.2.1]). *For every isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between two affine spaces X, Y , the bijections $\vec{F} : \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{Y}$ and $\ddot{F} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_Y$ have the following properties:*

- (1) $\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \ddot{F}(s \cdot t) = \ddot{F}(s) \cdot \ddot{F}(t);$
- (2) $\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \ddot{F}(s + t) = \ddot{F}(s) + \ddot{F}(t);$
- (3) $\forall \vec{x}, \vec{y} \in \vec{X} \quad \vec{F}(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) = \vec{F}(\vec{x}) + \vec{F}(\vec{y});$
- (4) $\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \forall \vec{v} \in \vec{X} \quad \vec{F}(s \cdot \vec{v}) = \ddot{F}(s) \cdot \vec{F}(\vec{v});$
- (5) $\forall o \in X \quad \forall \vec{v} \in \vec{X} \quad F(o + \vec{v}) = F(o) + \vec{F}(\vec{v}).$

For Desarguesian affine spaces, Proposition 21.1 turns into a characterization of isomorphisms between Desarguesian affine spaces.

Theorem 21.2 ([2, 18.2.3]). *A function $F : X \rightarrow Y$ between two Desarguesian affine liners X, Y is an isomorphism if and only if there exist bijective maps $\vec{F} : \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{Y}$ and $\ddot{F} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_Y$ such that the following conditions are satisfied:*

- (1) $\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \ddot{F}(s \cdot t) = \ddot{F}(s) \cdot \ddot{F}(t);$

- (2) $\forall s, t \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \ddot{F}(s+t) = \ddot{F}(s) + \ddot{F}(t);$
- (3) $\forall \vec{x}, \vec{y} \in \overrightarrow{X} \quad \vec{F}(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) = \vec{F}(\vec{x}) + \vec{F}(\vec{y});$
- (4) $\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \forall \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X} \quad \vec{F}(s \cdot \vec{v}) = \ddot{F}(s) \cdot \vec{F}(\vec{v});$
- (5) $\exists o \in X \quad \forall \vec{v} \in \overrightarrow{X} \quad F(o + \vec{v}) = F(o) + \vec{F}(\vec{v}).$

Proposition 21.3 ([2, 18.2.9]). *Let M be a set in a Desarguesian affine space X , o be a point of M and $B := M \setminus \{o\}$. The flat hull \overline{M} of the set M in X is equal to the set*

$$\Sigma := \{x \in X : \exists c \in \mathbb{R}_X^{\oplus B} \quad \vec{o}x = \sum_{b \in B} c(b) \cdot \vec{o}b\}.$$

Theorem 21.4 ([2, 18.2.10]). *Let M be a maximal independent set in a Desarguesian affine space X , o be a point in M and $B := M \setminus \{o\}$. For every point $x \in X$, there exists a unique function $c_x \in \mathbb{R}_X^{\oplus B}$ such that $\vec{o}x = \sum_{b \in B} c_x(b) \cdot \vec{o}b$. The map $c : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X^{\oplus B}$, $c : x \mapsto c_x$, is an isomorphism of liners.*

Theorem 21.4 implies the following important corollary.

Corollary 21.5 ([2, 18.2.11]). *Every Desarguesian affine space X is isomorphic to the liner $\mathbb{R}_X^{\oplus \dim(X)}$.*

Theorem 21.6 ([2, 18.2.12]). *An affine space X is Desarguesian if and only if X is isomorphic to an R -module over a corps $R \neq \{0, 1\}$.*

Theorem 21.7 ([2, 18.2.13]). *Let X, Y be two Desarguesian affine spaces and $I : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_Y$ be an isomorphism between their corps. Let M_X, M_Y be any maximal independent sets in the liners X, Y , respectively. Every bijection $f : M_X \rightarrow M_Y$ extends to a unique liner isomorphism $F : X \rightarrow Y$ such that $\vec{F} = I$.*

Theorem 21.7 implies the following isomorphic classification of Desarguesian affine spaces.

Corollary 21.8 ([2, 18.2.14]). *Two Desarguesian affine spaces X, Y are isomorphic if and only if $\|X\| = \|Y\|$ and the corps \mathbb{R}_X and \mathbb{R}_Y are isomorphic.*

Corollary 21.8 motivates the problem of recognizing isomorphic corps. For finite corps this problem has a well-known classical answer, due to Wedderburn (1905), Dickson (1905), Witt (1931), and Moore (1893).

Theorem 21.9 (Wedderburn–Dickson–Witt; [2, 18.6.1]). *Every finite corps is a field.*

Theorem 21.10 (Moore; [2, 18.6.6]). *Two finite fields are isomorphic if and only if they have the same cardinality.*

22. COORDINATE CHARTS ON LINES IN DESARGUESIAN AFFINE SPACES

Let L be a line in an affine space X . Given any distinct points $z, u \in L$, consider the function

$$\phi_{zu} : L \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}, \quad \phi_{zu} : x \mapsto \vec{zx}\vec{u},$$

assigning to every point $x \in L$ the portion $\vec{zx}\vec{u}$. Proposition 8.1 implies that the function $\phi_{zu} : L \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}}$ is surjective. If the affine space X is Desarguesian, then $\ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} = \mathbb{R}_X$ and the function $\phi_{zu} : L \rightarrow \ddot{X}_{\mathfrak{K}} = \mathbb{R}_X$ is bijective. In this case the function $\phi_{zu} : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$ is called a *coordinate chart* on the line L . The coordinate chart ϕ_{zu} identifies the line L with the corps \mathbb{R}_X . Under this identification, we have $\phi_{zu}(z) = \vec{zz}\vec{u} = 0$ and $\phi_{zu}(u) = \vec{zu}\vec{u} = 1$.

For four points $z, u, o, e \in L$ with $z \neq u$ and $o \neq e$, the bijective function

$$\phi_{zu} \circ \phi_{oe}^{-1} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$$

is called the *transition function* between the charts ϕ_{oe} and ϕ_{zu} .

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & L & \\ \phi_{oe} \swarrow & & \searrow \phi_{zu} \\ \mathbb{R}_X & \xrightarrow{\phi_{zu} \circ \phi_{oe}^{-1}} & \mathbb{R}_X \end{array}$$

Theorem 22.1 ([2, 19.1.3]). *Let L be a line in a Desarguesian affine space X , and $z, u, o, e \in L$ be points with $z \neq u$ and $o \neq e$. Then $\phi_{oe} \circ \phi_{zu}^{-1}(s) = s \cdot (\overrightarrow{ze\dot{u}} - \overrightarrow{zo\dot{u}}) + \overrightarrow{zo\dot{u}}$ for every scalar $s \in \mathbb{R}_X$.*

The following theorem yields a coordinate description of line affinities.

Theorem 22.2 ([2, 19.1.5]). *Let L, Λ be two lines in a Desarguesian affine space and $z, u \in L, o, e \in \Lambda$ be points with $z \neq u$ and $o \neq e$. For any function $F : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ and the function $\Phi := \phi_{oe} \circ F \circ \phi_{zu}^{-1} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *The function $F : L \rightarrow \Lambda$ is a line affinity;*
- (2) *$\exists a \in \mathbb{R}_X^* \exists b \in \mathbb{R}_X \forall s \in \mathbb{R}_X \Phi(s) = (s \cdot a) + b$.*

23. AFFINITIES, PORTIONALITIES AND SCALARITIES IN AFFINE SPACES

Definition 23.1. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X is called

- (1) an *affinity* if for every line $L \subset X$, the restriction $A|_L$ is a line affinity of X ;
- (2) a *portionality* if $Axyz \bowtie xyz$ for every line triple $xyz \in \ddot{X}$ in X ;
- (3) a *scalarity* if $Axyz \bowtie xyz$ for every Desarguesian line triple $xyz \in \ddot{X}$ in X .

Proposition 23.2 ([2, 19.2.2]). *For any automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of an affine space X , the following conditions hold.*

- (1) *If A is an affinity, then A is portionality.*
- (2) *If A is a portionality, then A is a scalarity.*

Therefore, for every automorphism of an affine space, we have the implications:

$$\text{affinity} \Rightarrow \text{portionality} \Rightarrow \text{scilarity}.$$

For Desarguesian affine spaces, those three notions are equivalent.

Theorem 23.3 ([2, 19.2.3]). *For any automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a Desarguesian affine space X , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) *A is an affinity;*
- (2) *A is a portionality;*
- (3) *A is a scalarity.*

Definition 23.4. An automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ of a Desarguesian affine space X is called *affine* if A satisfies the equivalent conditions of Theorem 23.3.

For an affine space X , let $\text{Aff}(X), \text{Aff}_P(X), \text{Aff}_S(X)$ be the subsets of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$, consisting of all affinities, portionalities, and scalarities, respectively.

Proposition 23.5 ([2, 19.2.6]). *For every affine space X , the sets $\text{Aff}(X), \text{Aff}_P(X), \text{Aff}_S(X)$ are normal subgroups of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ such that $\text{Aff}(X) \subseteq \text{Aff}_P(X) \subseteq \text{Aff}_S(X)$. If the affine space X is Desarguesian, then $\text{Aff}(X) = \text{Aff}_P(X) = \text{Aff}_S(X)$.*

Question 23.6. *Let an affine space X . Is there a dilation $A : X \rightarrow X$ such that $Axy \in \overrightarrow{yx}$ for every $x, y \in X$?*

Remark 23.7. The answer to Question 23.6 is affirmative in Thalesian affine spaces X : for every point $o \in X$, the homothety $H_o : X \rightarrow X, H_o : x \mapsto o + (-1) \cdot \overrightarrow{ox}$, has the required property. Here -1 is the opposite scalar to the scalar $1 \in \mathbb{R}_X$.

Let X be an affine space and \mathbb{R}_X be its scalar corps. For every automorphism $A : X \rightarrow X$ and every line triple xyz in X , the image $Axyz$ is a line triple in X . If the line triple xyz is Desarguesian, then so is the line triple $Axyz$. This observation allows us to define the map $\ddot{A} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$ assigning to every scalar $s \in \mathbb{R}_X$ the scalar $\ddot{A}(s) = \{Axyz : xyz \in s\}$. It is easy to see that the function $\ddot{A} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$ is an automorphism of the corps \mathbb{R}_X . For two automorphisms $A, B : X \rightarrow X$ and their composition $C = A \circ B$, the automorphism $\ddot{C} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$ is equal to the composition $\ddot{A} \circ \ddot{B}$ of the automorphisms \ddot{A}, \ddot{B} of the corps \mathbb{R}_X . This means that the correspondence $T : \text{Aut}(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X), T : A \mapsto \ddot{A}$, is a homomorphism from the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of the liner X into the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)$ of the corps \mathbb{R}_X . The definition

of a scalarity implies that the automorphism $\ddot{A} : \mathbb{R}_X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_X$ is the identity map of \mathbb{R}_X if and only if the automorphism A is a scalarity of X .

Proposition 23.8 ([2, 19.2.11]). *For every affine space X , the function*

$$\text{Aut}(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X), \quad A \mapsto \ddot{A},$$

is a homomorphism from the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of the liner X into the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)$ of the corps \mathbb{R}_X . The kernel of the homomorphism $\text{Aut}(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)$ coincides with the group $\text{Aff}_S(X)$ of scalarities.

24. AFFINE AUTOMORPHISMS OF DESARGUESIAN AFFINE SPACES

Propositon 23.8 and Theorem 23.3 imply the following characterization of affine automorphisms of Desarguesian affine spaces.

Corollary 24.1 ([2, 19.3.1]). *A self-map $F : X \rightarrow X$ on a Desarguesian affine space X is an affine automorphism of X if and only if there exists a bijective map $\vec{F} : \vec{X} \rightarrow \vec{X}$ satisfying the following conditions:*

- (1) $\forall \vec{x}, \vec{y} \in \vec{X} \quad \vec{F}(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) = \vec{F}(\vec{x}) + \vec{F}(\vec{y});$
- (2) $\forall s \in \mathbb{R}_X \quad \forall \vec{v} \in \vec{X} \quad \vec{F}(s \cdot \vec{v}) = s \cdot \vec{F}(\vec{v});$
- (3) $\exists o \in X \quad \forall \vec{v} \in \vec{X} \quad F(o + \vec{v}) = F(o) + \vec{F}(\vec{v}).$

Theorem 21.7 implies the following extension result.

Corollary 24.2 ([2, 19.3.2]). *For every bijection $B : M \rightarrow M'$ between two maximal independent sets M, M' in a Desarguesian affine liner X , there exists a unique affine automorphism $F : X \rightarrow X$ of X such that $F|_M = B$.*

Theorem 24.3 ([2, 19.3.3]). *Let X be a Desarguesian affine space, M be a maximal independent subset in X , and $\text{Aut}_M(X) := \{A \in \text{Aut}(X) : A|_M = 1_M\}$. Then $\text{Aut}_M(X)$ is a subgroup of the group $\text{Aut}(X)$ such that $\text{Aut}_M(X) \cap \text{Aff}(X) = \{1_X\}$, $\text{Aut}(X) = \text{Aff}(X) \cdot \text{Aut}_M(X)$ and the function $\text{Aut}_M(X) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)$, $A \mapsto A$, is a group isomorphism.*

A group G is called a *semidirect product* of groups A, B if there exist a normal subgroup $\tilde{A} \subseteq G$ and a subgroup $\tilde{B} \subseteq G$ such that \tilde{A} is isomorphic to A , \tilde{B} is isomorphic to B , $\tilde{A} \cap \tilde{B} = \{1_G\}$ and $G = \tilde{A} \cdot \tilde{B}$. In this case we write that $G = A \rtimes B$. This definition of a semidirect product and Theorem 24.3 imply the following description of the automorphism group of a Desarguesian affine space.

Corollary 24.4 ([2, 19.3.4]). *The automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a Desarguesian affine space X is a semidirect product $\text{Aff}(X) \rtimes \text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)$ of the groups $\text{Aff}(X)$ and $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)$.*

Corollary 24.4 motivates the problem of studying the automorphism groups of (finite) fields.

Let F be a finite field and p be its characteristic (which is the smallest number p such that $p \cdot 1 = 0$).

Lemma 24.5 ([2, 19.4.1]). *Let F be a finite field of characteristic p . For every $x, y \in F$,*

$$(x + y)^p = x^p + y^p.$$

Lemma 24.5 implies that for every finite field F of characteristic p , the function $\Phi : F \rightarrow F$, $\Phi : x \mapsto x^p$, is an endomorphism of the field F . Since $x^p = 0$ iff $x = 0$, the endomorphism Φ is injective. Since F is finite, the injectivity of Φ implies its surjectivity and bijectivity. Therefore, the map $\Phi : F \rightarrow F$, $\Phi : x \mapsto x^p$, is an automorphism of the field F , called the *Frobenius automorphism* of the field F , after Ferdinand Georg Frobenius (1849 – 1917) who proved the following classical theorem.

Theorem 24.6 (Frobenius; [2, 19.4.2]). *Let F be a finite field of character p and cardinality p^n for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The automorphism group $\text{Aut}(F)$ of the field F is cyclic of order n , generated by the Frobenius automorphism.*

Applying Corollary 24.4 and Theorem 24.6 we can calculate the cardinality of the automorphism group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of a finite Desarguesian affine space X and its normal subgroup $\text{Aff}(X)$, consisting of affine automorphisms.

Theorem 24.7 ([2, 19.5.1]). *For every finite Desarguesian affine space X , the group $\text{Aff}(X)$ of affine automorphisms of X has cardinality*

$$|\text{Aff}(X)| = r^d \cdot \prod_{k=0}^{d-1} (r^d - r^k),$$

where $d := \dim(X) = \|X\| - 1$ and $r := |\mathbb{R}_X|$.

Theorem 24.8 ([2, 19.5.2]). *For every finite Desarguesian affine space X , the group $\text{Aut}(X)$ of automorphisms of X has cardinality*

$$|\text{Aut}(X)| = |\text{Aut}(\mathbb{R}_X)| \cdot |\text{Aff}(X)| = n \cdot s^r \cdot \prod_{k=0}^{r-1} (s^r - s^k),$$

where $r := \|X\|$ and $s := |\mathbb{R}_X| = p^n$ for some prime number p and some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

25. THE ANDRÉ DESCRIPTION OF THALESIAN AFFINE SPACES

In this section we present an algebraic description of Thalesian affine spaces, due to André [1]. An equivalent geometric description was also suggested by Bruck and Bose [7]. The André description of Thalesian affine spaces is based on the notion of a spread of R -submodules of an R -module.

Definition 25.1. Let X be an R -module over a corps R . A family \mathcal{S} of R -submodules is called a *spread of R -submodules* in X if $X = \bigcup \mathcal{S}$ and $A \cap B = \{0\}$ for every distinct R -submodules $A, B \in \mathcal{S}$. A spread of R -submodules \mathcal{S} in X is called *direct* if $|\mathcal{S}| \geq 3$ and $X = A + B := \{a + b : a \in A, b \in B\}$ for any distinct R -submodules $A, B \in \mathcal{S}$.

Two R -modules X, Y are *isomorphic* if there exists a bijective function $F : X \rightarrow Y$ such that $F(x + y) = F(x) + F(y)$ and $F(r \cdot x) = r \cdot F(x)$ for every $x, y \in X$ and $r \in R$. These two properties of F are called the *additivity* and the *R -homogeneity* of the isomorphism F .

Lemma 25.2 ([2, 17.4.2]). *Let R be a corps and \mathcal{S} be a direct spread of R -submodules in an R -module X . Then any two R -submodules $A, B \in \mathcal{S}$ are isomorphic. Consequently, $\{0\} \neq S \neq X$ for every $S \in \mathcal{S}$.*

Theorem 25.3 (André; [2, 17.4.3]). *Let X be a Thalesian affine space and \mathcal{L} be the family of lines in X . For every line $L \subseteq X$, the set $\vec{L} := \{x \in \vec{X} : x \parallel L\}$ is an \mathbb{R}_X -submodule of the \mathbb{R}_X -module \vec{X} . The family $\vec{\mathcal{L}} := \{\vec{L} : L \in \mathcal{L}\}$ is a spread of \mathbb{R}_X -submodules of the \mathbb{R}_X -module \vec{X} . If X is a plane, then the spread of \mathbb{R}_X -submodules $\vec{\mathcal{L}}$ is direct and $|\vec{\mathcal{L}}| \geq 3$.*

The following theorem of André gives a general method of construction of non-Desarguesian Thalesian affine spaces.

Theorem 25.4 (André; [[2, 17.4.5]). *Let R be a corps and \mathcal{S} be a direct spread of R -submodules of an R -module X such that $|\mathcal{S}| \geq 3$ for every R -submodule $S \in \mathcal{S}$. Then X endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L} = \{S + x : S \in \mathcal{S}, x \in X\}$ is a Thalesian Playfair plane such that $S = \{L \in \mathcal{L} : o \in L\}$, where o is the neutral element of the additive group of the R -module X .*

Now we apply Theorem 25.4 to produce examples of non-Desarguesian Thalesian planes, called André planes.

Let R be a corps containing at least three elements and F be a subfield of R . Then R can be considered as an F -module. Observe that for every $a \in R^* := \{0\}$, the set $S_a := \{(x, x \cdot a) : x \in R\}$ is an F -submodule of the F -module $R \times R$, and $\mathcal{S} = \{S_a : a \in R^*\} \cup \{\{0\} \times R\}$ is a direct spread of R -submodules that determines the standard linear structure of the affine (Desarguesian) plane $R \times R$.

Now we modify the spread \mathcal{S} to produce a Thalesian Playfair plane which is not necessarily Desarguesian.

Fix any normal subgroup H of the multiplicative group $R^* := R \setminus \{0\}$ and let $\text{Aut}(R)$ be the group of F -linear automorphisms of the F -module R . In the group $\text{Aut}(R)$ consider the subgroup $\text{Aut}_H(R)$ consisting of automorphisms $\sigma \in \text{Aut}(R)$ such that $\sigma(x) \in H \cdot x = x \cdot H$ for all $x \in R^*$. Let $\sigma_* : R^* \rightarrow \text{Aut}_H(R)$, $\sigma_* : a \mapsto \sigma_a$, be any function such that for every $a \in R^*$, the set $\{\sigma_x : x \in H \cdot a\} \subseteq \text{Aut}_H(R)$ is a singleton. For every $a \in R^*$ consider the F -submodule $\tilde{S}_a := \{(x, \sigma_a(x) \cdot a) : x \in R\}$ of $R \times R$.

Proposition 25.5 ([2, 17.5.1]). *If the R -module has finite F -dimension, then the family*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}} := \{\tilde{S}_a : a \in R^*\} \cup \{\{0\} \times R, R \times \{0\}\}$$

*is a direct spread of F -modules in the F -module $R \times R$. The set $R \times R$ endowed with the family of lines $\mathcal{L} = \{S + x : S \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}, x \in R \times R\}$ is a Thalesian Playfair plane, called an **André plane**.*

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T. BANAKH: IVAN FRANKO NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LVIV (UKRAINE)
AND JAN KOCHANOWSKI UNIVERSITY IN KIELCE (POLAND)
Email address: t.o.banakh@gmail.com

I. HETMAN: LVIV (UKRAINE)
Email address: vespertilion@gmail.com

V. PSHYK: IVAN FRANKO NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF LVIV (UKRAINE)
Email address: pshik.vlad8@gmail.com